

INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA KASBGA OID LEKSIKANING
SHAKLLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI

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ELSEVIER

G.B.Ergasheva

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Magistratura bo'limi
Lingvistika (ingliz tili) yo'nalishi
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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillarida kasbga oid leksikaning o'rni, tillardagi faol leksik birliklar va ularning leksik-semantik xususiyatlari nimalardan iborat ekanligi haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi.

Keywords: Leksika, leksikografiya, leksik birliklar, kasb-hunar, so'zlar, tillar, frazeologiya, frazeologik birliklar, terminlar, lug'atlar.

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FEATURES OF FORMATION OF LEXICON RELATED TO PROFESSION IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

G.B. Ergasheva

Karshi State University
Graduate Department
Linguistics (English) major
Graduate student of group 022-9

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Abstract: This article provides information about the role of professional lexicon in Uzbek and English languages, active lexical units in the languages and what their lexical-semantic features are.

Keywords: Lexicon, lexicography, lexical units, profession, words, languages, phraseology, phraseological units, terms, dictionaries.

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Vocational lexicon - a set of words and concepts specific to the speech of the owners of a certain profession or profession. Borrowing words from another language, words specific to the dialect, words with a changed meaning specific to the national language are the main source for the formation of the lexicon of the profession. Different names of the same item or thing by different professions can also create a professional lexicon. The lexicon of the developed branch of the profession is rich, and separate literature related to these areas has been published. They are an important source in enriching the vocabulary of science and technology, in general, and in studying the history of material culture of the nation. Vocational lexicon serves as a means of artistic representation in the deeper

illumination of the characteristics and nature of a certain character in fiction. Mankind has always tried to feed itself, to satisfy its needs and interests, and it is still on this path. Man began to satisfy his needs, first of all, for food, shelter, clothing. Later, when new civilizations appeared, that is, as humanity became more civilized, it began to produce products for its needs. First of all, these created the desire to create professionals in this field and to satisfy the society's need for these products. As society developed, new professions appeared and developed. And people strive to live well and happily. Those who chose a profession for this, gained experience and gained knowledge. Profession is a type of activity, field, craft of human work that requires certain experience and training. The profession is achieved through general or specialized knowledge and practical experience. Within the profession, there are specialties that are distinguished by the narrowest nature of labor activity. Vocational guidance or career guidance is a whole psychological-pedagogical process of helping young people to acquire a profession. It is a process that takes into account the needs of society for specialists. Choosing a profession is a complex, but necessary process, which creates a person's future and opportunities for a better life, as well as finding his place in society and making useful work for him. Vocational guidance is a process of providing advice to pedagogues based on the abilities and interests of students, taking into account their psychological characteristics. One of the areas where the profession is related to the profession is the field of teaching, in which education and imparting knowledge, the process of formation of qualifications and skills, is the main means of preparing a person for life and work.

The development of the lexicon of the teaching profession is the use of foreign words in the educational process. As with all lexical resources of the Uzbek language, terms have their own ways of enrichment and they are in accordance with the general laws of the development of our language.

The view that there is not a single language in the world that has not acquired foreign words also corresponds to his terminology. "In all languages, to express a new concept, either a ready-made term from another language is adopted, or a word or term existing in this language is used, or a new term is created." It is also important to talk about. Examining the existing dictionaries shows that only a certain part of the terms related to the social life, profession and crafts of Uzbeks are included in them. Let's refer to some examples given in T.Tursunova's "Practical Lexicon of the Uzbek Language": zulkhirs, zulbarak, arabi, olacha, palos, kholi/gholi, sholcha, kokma, or bosma (1.chakmon. 2. ilma, type of seam), birishim, bozastar, gulburi, dorpech, dug/duk, dukhoba, shop (1. dastgoh, machine. 2. magazine), doppi yondori, joypush, zardevol/ zardevor, zardozi, zahdozhdok, yorma, peshonaband/peshonabag, popop, popomakhir, urchuq, chitel,

ramkorbash/ramkorok, etc. Among them, Arabic, palos, paddy words, which mean the types of carpets, as well as zardozi, zahdozlik, zardevol, popup, popomakhir, peshonaband, peshonabog, urchuq, which mean carpet, are listed in the dictionaries. Regardless of whether they are productive or not, standardized or not, these units should be recorded in dictionaries and preserved for future generations.

It is known that there are many words related to various fields of science and profession in the English and Uzbek language, and they are standardized in written and oral forms. We observe this especially in terms related to various fields of science, such as linguistics, literary studies, mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology, medicine, economics. At the moment, there are tools in the English and Uzbek language that cannot be limited to one field or one task style. If they were standardized with one meaning within one style or in a certain field, they were standardized with another meaning from another style or field. For example: unit, section, water circle, time, base, axis, plane, surface, while being common words, unit, surface, axis, plane in geometry, time in philosophy, basic construction - standardized as a term in architecture.

One word can be standardized in two ways, as a term in the field of science. For example, morphology:

1) in linguistics - the system of word change forms in the language, the section of grammar about the ways of forming word forms and the rules of word formation;

2) in botany - as a science that studies the structure and form of the soil; assimilation:

1) in biology - assimilation, absorption and digestion of organic substances during the activity of the organism;

2) in linguistics - in the pronunciation of words, the two sounds in their composition are coordinated with each other as a result of their interaction, are absorbed into each other, and become different;

3) in history and ethnography - as a result of a nation's assimilation of customs, culture, and language of another nation.

The opposite is also observed in language development. The range of meaning of terms belonging to a certain field of science or profession expands - the process of determination takes place, that is, they leave the scope of narrow terminology, become popular and begin to be used in all functional methods. For example: to operate a person - to carry out a currency operation - to carry out a military operation. In this way, they are also used in stable compounds: hegemony, to become an automaton, to have a high rating, to quote, etc.

There are also units that appear in the language at a certain time, are used mainly in colloquial speech, become standardized, and go out of use before entering the dictionaries. We can say the following about different materials and names of some clothes that women make dresses: bride wears, mother-in-law wears; such as margylan kopi, cabbage leaf, namazshomgul, tahir-zuhra, mermaid, scarle. In this way, we can continue the analysis of all professional words and language norms in the English and Uzbek language.

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